

From Fig. 2 it is observed that compared to unirradiated DNH there is hyperchromicity in uv irradiated solution. The absorbance values for unirradiated DNH at the same wavelengths as that

Fig. 2. Uv absorption spectra of unirradiated and uv irradiated DNH; concn. of DNH = $30 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, dose of uv irradiation = 900 erg mm^{-2} : (O) unirradiated DNH, and (●) uv irradiated DNH.

of DNA are 0.170 ± 0.03 , 0.190 ± 0.02 , 0.250 ± 0.02 and 0.280 ± 0.02 , hence the average value being 0.22. For irradiated DNH at the same wavelengths the absorbance values are 0.290 ± 0.04 , 0.310 ± 0.04 , 0.370 ± 0.05 and 0.390 ± 0.05 , the average value being 0.34. The average percentage hyperchromicity is 15.57%. So for the same concentration and dose, the average percentage hyperchromicity value for DNH is half than that of DNA. It has been reported⁹ that the change produced in DNA when irradiated as a nucleoprotein complex inside cells are qualitatively and quantitatively different from those that are produced when pure DNA is treated. In the present case, though it is not cellular nucleoprotein, the protein coat on DNA definitely protects it from uv radiation damage¹⁰.

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Synthesis of New Flavone

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THE isolation and characterisation of 5-*O*-methylacacetin (1) from the heartwood of *Adina cordifolia* has been reported previously by Srivastava¹. The present communication reports the synthesis² of 1 and its 7-*O*-methyl derivative (2). This synthesis of 1 further supports its structure.

Condensation of 4-*O*-benzyl-2-*O*-methylphloroacetophenone (3) and 2,4-di-*O*-methylphloroacetophenone with anisaldehyde in alkali yielded the corresponding chalcones 4 and 5, respectively, which on SeO_2 treatment afforded 7-*O*-benzyl-5-*O*-methylacacetin (6) and 5,7-di-*O*-methylacacetin (7), respectively. The acacetin (6) on debenzylation gave a product which was identical to the natural flavone (1). The required phloroacetophenone methyl ethers were prepared by methylation of phloroacetophenone³, while anisaldehyde was prepared by formylation of anisole^{4,5}.

Experimental

Methyl ethers of phloroacetophenone: A mixture of phloroacetophenone (4 g), anhydrous K_2CO_3 (10 g), Me_2SO_4 (3 ml) and dry Me_2CO (100 ml) was refluxed for 5 h and worked up. The product was separated by column chromatography over silica gel into 2,4-di-*O*-methyl- (m.p. $80-1^\circ$, 1.50 g), 4-*O*-methyl- (m.p. $139-40^\circ$, 800 mg) and 2-*O*-methylphloroacetophenones (m.p. $204-5^\circ$, 800 mg).

Synthesis of 1: 2-*O*-Methylphloroacetophenone (500 mg) was dissolved in dry Me_2CO (50 ml) and refluxed with benzyl chloride (4 ml) in the presence of K_2CO_3 (2 g) for 3 h⁶. Usual work-up and crystallisation from Me_2CO -EtOAc mixture yielded 3 (415 mg), m.p. $130-32^\circ$.

A mixture of 3 (400 mg) and anisaldehyde (440 mg) in EtOH (15 ml) containing aqueous NaOH

(60%, 10 ml) was kept at room temperature for 80 h. On acidification with dilute HCl, a solid was obtained which was extracted with ether (100 ml). The ethereal extract was washed with water and then concentrated to afford 4, then crystallising from ether-acetone mixture, (350 mg), m.p. 180–84°d; δ (CDCl₃, 90 MHz) 14.00 (s, OH), 7.85 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz, H- β), 7.65 (1H, d, *J* 16Hz, H- α) 7.60 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, *ortho*-coupled protons in B-ring), 7.30–7.40 (5H, m, C₆H₅), 6.92 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, *ortho*-coupled protons in B-ring), 6.05 (1H, d, *J* 2.5Hz, H-3'), 5.95 (1H, d, *J* 2.5Hz, H-5'), 5.19 (2H, d, CH₂Ph), 4.00 (3H, s, 1 × MeO) and 3.90 (3H, s, 1 × MeO).

Compound 4 (250 mg) in amyl alcohol (15 ml) was treated with SeO₂ (250 mg) as usual⁵ and the product 6 crystallised from C₆H₆-petroleum ether mixture, (200 mg), m.p. 120–23°; δ (CDCl₃, 90 MHz) 7.85 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, H-2' and 6'), 7.35–7.40 (5H, m, C₆H₅), 6.95 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, H-3' and 5'), 6.83 (1H, s, H-3), 6.40 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.20 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-6), 5.20 (2H, d, CH₂Ph) and 3.95 (3H, s, 1 × MeO).

The flavone, 6 (150 mg) was dissolved in EtOAc (40 ml) and Pd-C (10%, 100 mg)^{7,8} was added. The mixture was stirred under H₂-atmosphere for 5 h. The catalyst was filtered, solvent removed and the product crystallised from MeOH-Me₂CO mixture as microcrystalline yellow substance (110 mg), m.p. 160–63°d; δ (d₆-DMSO, 90 MHz) 10.82 (s, OH), 7.90 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, H-2' and 6'), 7.0 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, H-3' and 5'), 6.35 (1H, s, H-3), 6.40 (1H, d, *J* 2.5Hz, H-8), 6.20 (1H, d, *J* 2.5Hz, H-6), 4.0 (3H, s, 1 × MeO) and 3.90 (3H, s, 1 × MeO). It was identical to the natural sample 1.

Synthesis of 2: 2,4-Di-*O*-methylphloroacetophenone (500 mg) and anisaldehyde (500 mg) in EtOH (20 ml) containing aqueous NaOH (60%; 15 ml) was kept at room temperature for 80 h, and worked up as usual. The chalcone (5) was crystallised from ether-benzene mixture, (400 mg), m.p. 140–42°; δ (CDCl₃, 90 MHz) 14.0 (s, OH), 7.80 (1H, d, *J* 16Hz, H- β), 7.64 (1H, *J* 16Hz, H- α), 7.60 and 6.93 (2H each, both separate d, *J* 9Hz, *ortho*-coupled-H in B-ring), 6.03 (1H, d, *J* 2.5Hz, H-3'), 5.94 (1H, d, *J* 2.5Hz, H-5'), 4.0 (3H, s, 1 × MeO), 3.92 (3H, s, 1 × MeO) and 3.88 (3H, s, 1 × MeO).

Compound 5 (300 mg) in amyl alcohol (20 ml) was treated with SeO₂ (310 mg) as usual and the product, 2 was crystallised from Me₂CO-Et₂O mixture as yellow crystals (220 mg), m.p. 162–63° (lit.⁹ 162–63°); δ (DMSO-d₆, 90 MHz) 7.85 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, H-2' and 6'), 6.82 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, H-3' and 5'), 6.40 (1H, d, *J* 2.5Hz, H-8), 6.32 (1H, s, H-3), 6.20 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-6), 4.0 (3H, s, 1 × MeO), 3.97 (3H, s, 1 × MeO) and 3.92 (3H, s, 1 × MeO).

The compounds 1–6 gave satisfactory analytical data.

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Synthesis of some New 4-Methylcoumarins

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4-Methylcoumarins comprise of an important group of natural products. A few of them have been found to possess choleric¹, analgesic², antispermatogenic³ and diuretic⁴ properties. It has been observed¹ that coumarins carrying a 4-methyl function have much stronger choleric property than those lacking this functionality; furthermore, the metabolites of the former compounds were rapidly excreted while those of the latter compounds were slowly excreted. In view of these observations and better *in vivo* functioning and ease of excretion of their metabolites, we have carried out the synthesis of some new 4-methylcoumarins having (ethoxycarbonyl)methyl- and (ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl side chains at C-3 carbon atom via Pechmann reaction. 1,2,4-Trihydroxybenzene⁵ on condensation with α -acetyl diethyl succinate gave 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)methyl-4-methyl-6,7-dihydroxycoumarin (1). This on complete methylation and acetylation gave 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)methyl-4-methyl-6,7-dimethoxycoumarin (2) and 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)methyl-4-methyl-6,7-diacetoxycoumarin (3), respecti-